

Risk Assessment in Oil and Gas Construction in Yemen

Ammar Mohammed Hussain Al-Nahari¹, Du Hong Xiu^{2*}, Hashem Musaed Ahemd Al-Qarwaei¹, Mohamed Kadar Abdiaziz³

¹Postgraduate Student, Department of Civil Engineering, Taiyuan University of Technology

²Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Taiyuan University of Technology

³Postgraduate Student, Department of Mining, Taiyuan University of Technology

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*Corresponding Author:
Du Hong Xiu

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Risk assessment is one of the most basic instruments utilized in the security building framework in oil and gas construction extends because of it giving the necessary insurance to the development activities, for example, pilling, materials manufacture, and structure establishment. In oil and gas construction ventures numerous chronicled oil slick and failures happened because of an absence of productive risk evaluation in the development stage, and human life misfortunes. There are different elements that add to the execution issue in the development stage, in this way, various perspectives ought to be broke down in the risk appraisal structures to decide how the framework is firmly connected. Numerous researchers attempt to break down the usage issue in the oil and gas division, alongside other substantial ventures, through hazard guidelines, chance arranging and human blunder. This examination uncovered the deformities and difficulties in the hazard evaluation in oil and gas development extends in Yemen through a poll study. The exploration shows a hole in the comprehension and practice of the hazard evaluation among the board and activity, especially in the behavioural effects. The present study shows the comparison between two big companies in Yemen.

Keywords: RISK ASSESSMENT; RISK ANALYSIS; YEMEN

1.1 Aim of The Research

The current research aimed to study the change in the assessment of risk factors in the construction projects by the participants in the questionnaire and developing a Risk Assessment framework. Although that the research was conducted to identify the significant risk factors in construction projects for oil and gas processing facilities in Yemen, the results can be applied to construction projects implemented in any of developing countries

1.2 Introduction

Due to its provision of the necessary protection for construction activities such as pilling, product

processing or structure installation, Risk Assessment is one of the most important methods used in engineering projects on oil and gas construction. The main objective of the Risk Assessment Tool is to ensure that four essential elements of the oil industry can be fully protected. Failure or failure in the execution of the risk assessment in the construction phase will lead to disasters in the advanced phases such as development and operations. Most recent oil spills and blast outs in oil and gas construction projects are caused by a lack of successful risk assessment during building phases leading to financial and human life losses. Different factors contribute to the implementation issue during the building phase. Various aspects of the risk assessment processes should be examined to evaluate the closeness of the system. This work highlights the shortcomings and the challenges posed by a questionnaire survey in the risk assessment system oil and gas construction projects. The research shows a difference, particularly in behavioral effects, in understanding and using the risk assessment method between management and service. Implementing risk assessment is not a new challenge for the oil and gas safety technology environment. Many well-known case studies on failing risk assessment are the result of a lack of implementation in the field of risk assessment.

Construction is an industry with several challenges, which is quite dynamic und complex. The prevention and mitigation of all essential risk factors can be carried out by proper assessment of Risk factors. That can be done by ensuring security matters are enforced throughout the life-cycle construction project. The authors believe that, due to the complexity of construction factors with a social, human and economic dimension, construction industry has a high accident-related rate compared to others. Examples of these dimensions are inadequate education, large number of subcontractors, lack of pro-active culture, and the risk assessment is inadequate. The authors mention that in the design stage these negative factors can be prevented and managed before they escalate and affect the project. This can be achieved using detailed Risk-identification methods like Task Risk Assessment (TRA) and Hazard and Operability Studies (HAZOP). If a specific system exists, such as the health, security and Environmental Management Framework (HSE-MS), all problems within the enterprise can be handled and enforced effectively.

2.1 Method of Research

The reason for this examination is to assess the utilization of the risk assessment strategy for actualizing the wellbeing designing system for oil and gas development in Yemen between three organizations. To this end, we will examine the accompanying three objectives: logical, procedural, and social, where the destinations incorporate three viewpoints.

The Qualitative information on the part of the human factor in the usage of security should be gathered. Poll studies give a powerful method of completing this test, since they assist the inspector with being nearer to the universe of the worker and to screen their difficulties and those influencing their conduct wellbeing. he survey covers the accompanying focuses:

1. Familiarity with Risk assessment-based tools.
2. The courses for safety and risk assessment.
3. Safety and risk assessment officer for the evaluations.
4. Role and responsibilities towards the job in oil and Gas Company.
5. Maintenance and emergencies workshops provided by the company.
6. Working hours and load on the staff during the constructions.
7. The actions taken by the top managements during the occurrence of hazards inside the fields.

2.2 Method of Analysis

A defined irregular examining is the inspecting approach utilized for this investigation. Most security innovation specialists see overlaid arbitrary examining as a compelling technique for assessing wellbeing quality in building and different areas. The accompanying condition and boundaries were utilized for the Z score test:

3.1 Results and Analysis

A survey serves four capacities—empowers information assortment from respondents, loans a design to interviews, gives a standard way to recording answers and help in preparing gathered information. A poll will be ineffectual on the off chance that it isn't planned in a way effortlessly comprehended by both the questioner and the interviewee. The plan is reliant on the specialist's choice to gather subjective information for better arrangement and age of speculations regarding a matter (exploratory examination), or quantitative information to test explicit theories Figure 3-1

Figure 3-1: Familiarity with risk assessment-based tools

The primary issue concerned assessment of the degrees of information on representatives working in oil and gas development organizations with Risk Assessment techniques. Considering Figure 3-1, one can contend that most the workers need adequate information on these instruments. Over half in everywhere on the organizations who oppose this idea. This can demonstrate an absence of preparing for the development workers which can cause genuine security issues because of the high openness level with all recognized possible dangers. Chapman guarantees that most development organizations don't give specialized security courses to their workers. This is particularly obvious on account of development workers.

Figure 3-2: Quality of risk assessment within the company

This clarifies why many end clients do not have even the central comprehension of their association's security development methods. Accordingly, the inquiry refers to "adequate" to contemplate the assessment of the respondent on the instructional classes the individual gets. As Fig shows. 3-2, over half don't accept they have sufficient security courses needed for their positions particularly in Safer and Total organization. Nonetheless, 42% disagree for the courses given by the Yemen LNG. Also, 10% of the staffs who are fulfilled by the flowed gave altogether and Yemen LNG. Notwithstanding, around 20% who concur about the courses in Safer Company.

Figure 3-3: Understanding the role and responsibilities of Risk Assessment

Figure 3-3 shows the arrangement and obligations towards the security among the worker in the three organizations. Initially, 60%, 55%, 61% of the staffs in Yemen, and Total separately concur that large portions of the end client staff comprehend their security duties. The second class in Yemen LNG, and Total individually came generally from building laborers or top chiefs who didn't completely comprehend their wellbeing commitments. This is an exceptionally stressing result, as these two positions would perceive their insurance duties in a solid manner.

4.1 Developing and Analyzing the Risk Framework

The aim of this study is to provide an integrated framework that can optimize the implementation of the safety in construction through the usage of a risk assessment. The questionnaire exposed the presently weak areas in the risk assessment application thereby aiding the selection of the framework inputs in this research. As shown in the Figure 4-1, there are three main sections employed as filters during the hazard identification stage in which each one of them has specific criteria. Such a focus will facilitate avoiding the kind generalizations practiced in most risk assessment sessions to cover all the possible scenarios that can occur with the existing risk.

Figure 4-1: Integrated Risk Assessment Framework

Each group has three standards that should clarify the identified hazard, its dimension and interaction mechanism with the wanted construction activity. Following this full examination, a regular risk assessment procedure is carried out where risk estimation and evaluation will be conducted in the General Risk Characterization stage. At the same time, risk monitoring will be involved in all steps to facilitate a healthy communication between the parties, especially the management and end-users. There are three main steps that should be followed:

1. Define the construction process based on activity analysis
2. Develop and write the procedures
3. Monitor the procedures enforcement

Figure 4-2: Risk assessment application steps

The proposed Framework in Figure 4-2 is more conceptual where it may cause some complications for construction organizations during the implementation process. For that, an implementation plan is developed that contains practical guidelines that can ease the execution process for the industrial sectors.

This framework presents integration between construction engineering and risk assessment through functional analysis that explains the equipment parts and their utilities. This would help fill the gap in the questionnaire, especially in the machineries and equipment failures. There are several scholars who strongly believe that there is a lack of technical examination for the current automotive safety technology at the construction site Figure 4-3.

Figure 4-3: Risk functional analysis

In the failure parts, it shows how recourse management is needed to mitigate the risk. As a result of this

exposure which demonstrate that explicit mitigation acts, putting prevention safety barriers will be more systematic with respect to the environment of the construction project. The failure of a single component in design stage can cause the failure for the whole system thus highlighting why identifying potential single-point failures is essential for determining problem. For example, cladding at the site can be divided to the following sub activities; installation, fabrication, reviewing the specification, and supervision/communication. The following single barriers can be added for each subsystem as shown in Table 4-1.

Table 4-1: Risk Components analysis

Component	Risks
Installation	Lack of knowledge of the installers
Fabrication	Lack of sealing and drainage
Reviewing the specification	No compliance at the construction process to reduce cost
Supervision/communication	Workload/ commercial pressure

Moreover, many designers prefer this way of analysis when it comes for materials selection to choose the right feature for suitable performance against the process construction and operation phases and factors that may lead to the failure mood.

Figure 4-4: Risk maintenance strategy

The questionnaires and interviews helped unveil all technical defects in the functional analysis and failure modes. Many construction professionals believe in the need of involving the maintenance strategy in the risk assessment of the project. The authors describe how the current usage of these strategies in the organization requires a more specified focus. That is, traditional maintenance strategies may not achieve the production and safety goals because they are designed to preform before or after equipment breakdown. Such a superficial

understanding of the role of maintenance strategy prompts management to make questionable decisions that translate into accidents at the construction site. As such, a new methodology will be introduced in this framework which involves border dimensions of the maintenance strategy, such as audit and leadership

Figure 4-5: Risk Assessment monitoring plan

As shown in Figure 4-5 that monitoring plan involves all the gardens of the employees in the organization in two main phases. The design and operation phases include variety of communication dimensions that aid each employee in office or site to implement the integrated risk assessment progressively.

5.1 Conclusion

Reviews and analyses of the lesson learned status of risk assessment and plan in the risk identification stage would help in obtaining a better risk breakdown structure and that will strengthen risk identification implementation. Risk categories that are used in the oil and gas industry are; technical support, procurement and materials, startup & operations, field execution & logistics and organization and communications. This questionnaire shows the gap between management and end users. Such differences become even more apparent as 75% of participants in the questionnaire discuss the compartmental protection side of building operations. This is critical because even if all potential procedural and technical hazards are assessed without considering the behavioral safety factors, it will not be effective to simply guarantee the integrated safety at the site. For instance, according to

Due to that, further investigation is necessary to understand the reasons and risk factors behind why these challenges exist inside the construction organization, particularly between senior management and laborer's. Such an investigation will help reach the aim of this study i.e., providing an integrated framework to optimize the safety engineering system in the oil and gas industry. This can be approached through interviewing construction professions who possess a complete view pertaining to the current barriers and issues for safety implementation at the construction sites.

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